

JammAI: a combinatorial approach to Music Co-Creation

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1 Problem statement

Given a set of music samples s where each sample is associated with a set of metadata s_m and a set of track roles $R \subseteq \{main_melody, accompaniment, riff\dots\}$, the problem is to find $|R|$ sequences of samples of the same length such that the metadata and the characteristics of the samples satisfy a number of constraints and maximise (resp. minimise) a given objective function.

Intuitively, the constraints guarantee that the sequences of samples satisfy a minimal set of theoretical music conventions such as:

- It is required that all the samples have the same time signature (e.g. 4/4);
- It is required that samples of a given track be played with the same instrument (or belong to the same family of instruments);
- It is required that all the samples occurring in a segment across different tracks (e.g. the samples occurring as the first in a track) have the same number of measures. Possibly, a sample might occur twice in a segment to fulfil the required number of measures.

Intuitively, the objective function embodies the preferences of the artist being assisted. This function is the combination of multiple scores associated with:

- Music Samples;
- Sequence of samples;
- Samples and sequence position.

These functions could be learned in an RL setting.

Figure 1 shows an example of a problem instance. The problem requires the generation of two tracks, namely the main melody and the accompaniment, each comprising four segments (see Figure 1a). The samples are to be chosen from the dataset depicted in Figure 1b. The dataset contains N samples associated with metadata, such as Time Signature, Num of Measures, Track Role etc.

Figure 1: An example of problem instance

Figure 1c shows a solution in which Sample 1 is repeated four times to fill the main melody segments. Interestingly, the first segment of the accompaniment is filled with Sample 2 repeated twice to match the number of measures (8) of Sample 1 in the main melody.

2 Materials

As a reference set of samples, we adopted ComMU [1]. ComMU is a symbolic music dataset containing 11,144 MIDI samples that consist of short note sequences that are manually composed by professional composers with its corresponding 12 metadata (bpm, genre, key, instrument, track-role, time signature, pitch range, number of measures, chord progression, min/max velocity, and rhythm).

3 Approach

We have framed music generation as a constraint optimisation problem.

Problem definition. Given a set of music samples $s \in D$ where each sample is associated with a set of metadata s_m and a set of track roles $R \subseteq \{tr_1 \dots tr_n\}$, the problem is to find $|R|$ sequences of samples of a given length l such that the metadata and the characteristics of the samples satisfy a number of constraints and maximise (resp. minimise) a given objective function.

In the following, we introduce the variables, the constraints and the objective function of the problem.

Variables. Given a dataset of music samples D , we denote with $D(x)$ the subset of D containing only the samples with track role x , e.g. $D(\text{main melody})$ contains all the samples with track role “main melody”. Without loss of generality, we translate the set $D(x)$ into an ordered sequence of samples. In doing so, each sample in $D(x)$ is univocally assigned to an integer identifier ranging from 1 to $|D(x)|$. For each track role $r \in R$, we create l (one for each segment in the track) vectors of variables of size $|D(r)|$. Each variable is uniquely assigned to a sample and segment in a track role. The variable can take on two values: 1 if the sample is assigned to the segment, and 0 otherwise. For example, suppose that $l = 2$, $R = \{\text{main melody}, \text{accompaniment}\}$, $D(\text{main melody}) = [s_1^{mm}, s_2^{mm}, s_3^{mm}]$ and $D(\text{accompaniment}) = [s_1^a, s_2^a, s_3^a, s_4^a]$, the vectors of variables are

$$\vec{x}_1^{mm} = (x_{11}^{mm} \quad x_{12}^{mm} \quad x_{13}^{mm}) \quad \vec{x}_2^{mm} = (x_{21}^{mm} \quad x_{22}^{mm} \quad x_{23}^{mm})$$

$$\vec{x}_1^a = (x_{11}^a \quad x_{12}^a \quad x_{13}^a \quad x_{14}^a) \quad \vec{x}_2^a = (x_{21}^a \quad x_{22}^a \quad x_{23}^a \quad x_{24}^a)$$

\vec{x}_{ij}^{tr} is 1 if the j -th sample is chosen for the i -th segment of the track tr .

Moreover, for each track role $tr \in R$, we create l (one for each segment in the track) vectors of variables of size $|D(tr)|$. These vectors are needed to compute the number of repetitions of each sample of a segment. Therefore, the domain of the variables is 1 or 2.

$$\vec{r}_1^{mm} = (r_{11}^{mm} \quad r_{12}^{mm} \quad r_{13}^{mm}) \quad \vec{r}_2^{mm} = (r_{21}^{mm} \quad r_{22}^{mm} \quad r_{23}^{mm})$$

$$\vec{r}_1^a = (r_{11}^a \quad r_{12}^a \quad r_{13}^a \quad r_{14}^a) \quad \vec{r}_2^a = (r_{21}^a \quad r_{22}^a \quad r_{23}^a \quad r_{24}^a)$$

\vec{r}_{ij}^{tr} is 2 if the j -th sample is repeated twice in i -th segment of the track tr .

Constraints. It must be satisfied that exactly one sample is selected for each segment of each track.

$$\sum_{x_{si}^{tr} \in x_s^{tr}} x_{si}^{tr} = 1 \text{ for } tr \in R \text{ and } s \in \{1..l\},$$

All the samples occurring in a segment across different tracks (e.g. the samples occurring as the first in a track) have the same number of measures. A sample might occur twice in a segment to fulfil the required number of measures.

$$\text{AllEqual} \left(\sum_{i \in D(tr_1)} (\vec{x}_s^{tr_1} \cdot \vec{r}_s^{tr_1} \cdot \vec{m}^{tr_1})_i, \dots, \sum_{i \in D(tr_n)} (\vec{x}_s^{tr_n} \cdot \vec{r}_s^{tr_n} \cdot \vec{m}^{tr_n})_i \right) \text{ for } s \in \{1..l\}$$

where \vec{m}_i^{tr} (i.e. the i -th component of the vector \vec{m}^{tr}) is the number of measures of the i -th sample of the track tr .

All the samples occurring of a track are played with the same instrument (or belong to the same family of instruments).

$$\text{AllEqual}(\vec{x}_1^{tr} \cdot \vec{in}^{tr}, \dots, \vec{x}_l^{tr} \cdot \vec{in}^{tr}) \text{ for } tr \in R$$

where \vec{in}_i^{tr} (i.e. the i -th component of the vector \vec{in}^{tr}) is an integer identifying the instrument of the i -th sample of the track tr .

Objective function.

$$\max \sum_{i \in D(tr_1)} \sum_{s \in \{1..l\}} \sum_{tr \in R} \bar{x}_{si}^{tr} \sigma(tr, i)$$

where $\sigma(tr, i)$ is a score assigned to the i -th sample of the track tr .

References

- [1] Lee, H., Kim, T., Kang, H., Ki, M., Hwang, H., Park, K., Han, S., Kim, S.J.: Commu: Dataset for combinatorial music generation. In: Koyejo, S., Mohamed, S., Agarwal, A., Belgrave, D., Cho, K., Oh, A. (eds.) Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 35: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2022, NeurIPS 2022, New Orleans, LA, USA, November 28 - December 9, 2022 (2022)